

The Kardashians are a Danger to Culture, Intellect, Empathy, Compassion, and Mental Health

I know I might “cop some flack” for my acidic views within and, to a point, my hypocrisy; however, I never shy away from the truth, including the reality behind this juggernaut of clownishness and gaucheness that has been cruelly imposed on humankind! And I have been silent for several decades (which probably explains my acidity — perhaps I am the one who requires therapy over this debacle!). It is difficult to overestimate the horror the Kardashians have unleashed upon the world. From their pathetic narcissism to their talentless and vacuous media buffoonery, they are an affront to any semblance of intellectual rigour or general edification; it is no wonder how these creatures of vapid celebrity have managed to stay in our collective public consciousness for so long. We may never truly understand what led us into this abyss of fake, obtuse personas and intellectually deficient dialogues. Still, one thing is sure: all hope for a cultural rebirth must begin with denouncing the worst possible things that the Kardashians have inflicted on us. Here are my views in more detail.

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for Nico

(Image of the Kardashians by People Magazine: “Fair Use”)

With their money, fame and outrageous sense of self-importance, the Kardashians have had a tremendous impact on our society since they burst on the scene more than a decade ago. Their “reality” TV shows and tabloid appearances have set a dangerous precedent by teaching people it is acceptable to live tastelessly and irresponsibly. The Kardashians have become *the* symbols of shallow materialism in modern culture.

As their fame and presence in pop culture have grown, they have had an insidious effect on our cultural values, reinforcing values such as vanity, superficiality, and consumerism over compassion, empathy, loyalty, and respect for others. Not only do they threaten critical thought and authentic culture with their superficial display of “success”, but their false representation of reality that millions of viewers are exposed to can lead to behavioural and mental health deficiencies. The Kardashians are dangerous to authentic culture, intellectual progress, genuine human connection, and our minds.

Who Watches These People and Why?

(Image by Lab Manager: “Fair Use”)

Let us start with the psychology of reality TV, which is at the heart of the Kardashians’ success. Having the Kardashians on whilst making dinner is one thing, but to sit down and immerse yourself in them is quite another. Reality TV often speaks to the weak neediness of its viewers, who vainly seek validation through shallow shows with vacuous topics. The psychology behind such phenomena is complex; in particular, it speaks to the insecurity and primordial need for attention that lurks deep within human nature.

Even though the public may appear as active, passive viewers on the surface, they are actually contributing to a collective longing for something bigger than themselves. Reality TV satisfies these cravings while promoting voyeurism with thinly-veiled attempts at providing an honest reflection of our lives. These elements continue to make reality TV prevalent in a society where acknowledgement and acceptance are (*believed to be*) paramount.

(I invite you to think about the word “reality” as you look at this charming family portrait. Image by People Magazine: “Fair Use”)

More specifically, despite the irrational rage and justified indignation of those who fail to grasp what the Kardashian phenomenon represents, a select few out there would actually find things to admire in them. These people will tend to be those with a particular intellectual deficiency that allows them to turn a blind eye towards their self-centred behaviour and lack of achievement beyond fame.

To those weak individuals who need validation from society and constantly idolise shallow, vacuous celebrities, the Kardashians would likely be their cup of tea. However, it is incomprehensible that anyone else would subscribe to the almost toxic amount of attention dedicated to this particular family. Individuals with any ounce of self-respect and intelligence have been driven away from the adoration surrounding them. Behind the charisma lies a fake world crafted to absorb as many impressionable minds as possible. To all others, this serves only as an annoyance and an embarrassment towards modern culture and its weak worshippers.

The Rise of Materialism and Consumerism:

(Image by People Magazine: “Fair Use”))

The Kardashians have been incredibly successful in using their fame to promote a culture of consumerism and materialism. Through their reality TV shows, social media accounts, and product launches, they have used their influence to convince people that having an abundance of expensive possessions is desirable. Sadly, many people have bought into this idea and now believe they need vast amounts of cash (or, even worse, credit) and luxury items to be happy. This focus on material possessions has shifted away from more meaningful activities like education, volunteering, or self-improvement. This focus on external objects instead of internal values leads young people down a dangerous path away from true happiness and fulfillment.

Furthermore, the way that the Kardashians present themselves is often far removed from reality — they often present themselves as being wealthy beyond measure while also claiming to be “*just like us*” despite living lives that are anything but ordinary or relatable. Consequently, they create an unrealistic standard of beauty and success that young people feel obligated to live up to fit into society’s ideals. This can lead them down paths of self-destruction, such as low self-esteem or even eating disorders, due to their attempts at achieving unattainable goals set by celebrities simply trying to maintain their image and status in society.

The Kardashian family has used social media platforms such as Instagram and Twitter to continuously create buzz about themselves — oftentimes posting images or stories that are entirely fabricated but seem real enough for people to buy into them without question. This kind of exploitation not only perpetuates false narratives but also distracts from more critical issues facing our society, like poverty alleviation, bullying, and hate (including racism, sexism, homophobia, transphobia, etc.), which should be given more attention instead of being overshadowed by trivial matters like what Kim Kardashian wore last night or whom she was seen with this morning. More on Kim “literally” Kardashian further below.

Superficiality Over Substance:

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I'm losing
brain cells ...

(Image with permission)

Another issue with the Kardashian’s influence is that it promotes superficiality over substance. The family often posts pictures or videos showing off their expensive cars or clothes without any real context or meaning behind it — simply showing off for the sake of showing off. This behaviour reinforces the idea that you should be judged by your possessions rather than your character or talent.

Everybody knows that psychological studies have shown that excessive use of social media can lead to various mental health issues, from depression to anxiety and even suicidal thoughts. This is particularly true when that social media directly pertains to watching reality shows like *Keeping Up with the Kardashians*. Watching celebrities online live luxurious lifestyles can make viewers or consumers feel like they are “less than” or not good enough due to their own financial struggles. It can also lead to envy and jealousy as viewers or consumers compare their lives to those of the stars on screen.

This idea is especially damaging for those who cannot afford luxurious possessions or clothes due to financial constraints. This thinking also undermines any sense of communal spirit between groups as everyone competes with each other instead of working together towards a common goal.

How We Should Respond:

(“Teaching with Google Arts and Culture”)

Walking outdoors or reading a book might be a good start (or try both at once!).

(Image by AmReading)

Given all this information about why the Kardashians are a threat to authentic culture, it is essential for us all (especially youth and mental health workers) to take action to protect our young and vulnerable people from falling victim to these shallow messages. We should encourage critical thinking when it comes to consuming media (for example, by questioning why someone is promoting a specific message or product) and provide alternative forms of entertainment (such as books or educational videos) that promote positive values rather than superficial ones. Additionally, we should strive for greater diversity among those who appear in media so that young people have more relatable figures they can look up to instead of blindly following celebrities with no redeeming qualities other than their wealth or fame.

As stated above, the Kardashian family has been criticised for promoting an image focused solely on outward appearance rather than intellect or personal growth. This is especially true regarding their children, who are often seen wearing expensive designer clothing and participating in activities such as modelling photoshoots and fashion shows instead of engaging in activities that would benefit them intellectually, such as reading books or learning new skills. This sends a damaging message to young people who are easily influenced by celebrity culture; it teaches them that looks are far more valuable than intelligence or knowledge, which can stunt their own personal development and intellectual capacity.

Furthermore, that family is also guilty of normalising poor behaviour, whether cheating on spouses or engaging in reckless activities with no regard for consequences. These actions convey that it is okay to act up because someone will always be willing to forgive you or look past your mistakes due to your celebrity status or wealth. This

attitude is dangerous because it encourages young people — particularly those who are easily influenced — to make bad decisions without considering how it may affect their lives or reputation in the long run.

It also stunts personal development and intellectual capacity.

The Problem with Kim; Specifically:

(Here? Kim “literally” Kardashian. Image by People Magazine: “Fair Use”)

In addition to exploiting herself for personal gain, Kim Kardashian has also been accused of exploiting the bodies of others for her own gain. In 2017, she released a line of shapewear called “Kimono,” which drew backlash from critics who saw it as an example of cultural appropriation. Similarly, she has been accused of using transgender models in fashion campaigns without giving them proper credit or payment for their work.

It is nothing short of outrageous that Kim Kardashian would defile the iconic dress worn by Marilyn Monroe as a “tribute” to her, a stunt for attention. It is genuinely nauseating that “the pinnacle of Kim’s narcissism and failure to grasp reality” involved recreating a moment in history with her own likeness instead of appreciating the beauty, skill and passion that went into creating the original work. The audacity with which she can be so utterly self-centred speaks volumes about her disregard for anyone else’s experience. To say it is a disservice to Monroe, who was an icon even in her own time, would be vastly underestimating how resounding this failure is. It strips away every ounce of respect and admiration we could possibly have for Kim, who should be ashamed of her part in this heinous crime against fashion and authentic celebrity culture.

(Kimmy squeeEEEEEEEEEEzing into Marilyn Monroe’s famous dress. Image by LADBible: “Fair Use”)

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(The Damage is Done: Credits on Image)

Perhaps most concerning about Kim Kardashian's influence is how she has perpetuated certain negative stereotypes about women that are deeply rooted in our society — precisely the idea that women should be judged primarily on their appearance rather than their accomplishments or character traits. This notion can be especially damaging to young people who might look up to Kim Kardashian without understanding the implications behind her actions or words.

(Image by People Magazine: “Fair Use”)

From her self-promoting Instagram posts to her barely-concealed attempts to remain relevant, it is clear that Kim Kardashian suffers from extreme narcissism. This type of selfish behaviour turns off many people who are not as enamoured with celebrity culture as she believes they should be. Furthermore, it sends out a message that if you want to succeed in life, you must do whatever it takes — even if it means sacrificing your moral values or integrity.

Given that Kim Kardashian is arguably one of the most famous celebrities in the world today, it stands to reason that she wields considerable influence over young and vulnerable people whom her words or actions may easily sway. Unfortunately for them, what they often see from Kim does not reflect real-life values or morals; instead, she often promotes materialism and superficiality above all else. This can lead young

people down a path that could damage their personal development and well-being in later life.

From her relentless narcissism to her irresponsible influence over young and vulnerable people — there are plenty of reasons why Kim Kardashian may have earned herself a reputation as one of the most woeful celebrities on Earth today. Her rise to fame was not earned. Instead, it was built on a foundation of something much less tangible — her willingness to exploit her body and participate in questionable activities such as the 2007 sex tape with her boyfriend of the day. **Slow clap**

(Image by Cosmopolitan: “Fair Use”)

Conclusion:

The Kardashian family has long threatened mental health stability, perpetuating an unrealistic and fake “perfect lifestyle” to the public. Without any intellectual or narrative depth, their “Just Do It” mentality has seen many young viewers attempt to emulate this “perfection”, leading to low self-esteem and other psychological struggles. At the same time, the Kardashian family seems oblivious, selfishly reaping the rewards without respect for its audience’s mental well-being. It truly is a disgraceful show of intellectually backward content, threatening the mental health of billions across the globe — it’s time society takes a stance against this abhorrent family, which has no regard for our evolving psychology.

In conclusion, the Kardashians’ influence has had far-reaching effects on our society — from promoting a culture of materialism and superficiality to distracting young people

from pursuing meaningful activities like education or volunteer work (i.e., thinking about people other than themselves). We must recognise how damaging this kind of influence can be if we want our society to focus on meaningful connections and authentic experiences rather than flashy displays of wealth and status symbols. It is time for us all to reject these ideals perpetuated by the Kardashians if we want our society to continue developing positively towards true success with compassion, empathy, intelligence, and wisdom.

I'm losing
brain cells...

(Image with permission)